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FREE AND FORCED CONVECTIVE FLOW OF A SECOND GRADE FLUID IN A VERTICAL CHANNEL WITH THE EFFECTS OF RADIATION AND MAGNETIC FIELD

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Abstract

In this paper we investigate the effect of magnetic field on the fully developed free and forced convective flow of a second grade fluid in a vertical channel with permeable walls under the influence of radiation. It is assumed that the flow is steady and fully developed. The governing non-linear equations are solved for the velocity field and the temperature field using the traditional perturbation technique. The effects of various emerging parameters like visco-elastic parameter (k), Hartmann number (M), Cross-flow Reynolds number (R), Reynolds number (Re), Prandtl number (Pr), radiation parameter (N), Grashof number (Gr), wall temperature parameter (rT) are discussed in detail through graphs.

1. Introduction

The subject of Heat transfer in mixed convection in vertical channels under the influence

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of magnetic field widely occurs in many industrial processes and natural phenomena. Magnetohydrodynamics is currently undergoing an era of great enlargement and differentiation of subject matter. The interests in these new problems generates from their importance in liquid metals, electrolytes and ionized gases, fossil fuel, combustion, energy process, solar energy and space vehicle re-entry, control of pollutant spread in ground water, to name just a few applications. Boulama and Galanis [4] have investigated the fully developed mixed convection between parallel vertical plates with heat and mass transfer. Barletta et al. [2] have studied the Dual mixed convection flows in a vertical channel. Chamkha[5] have analyzed free convection effects on three-dimensional flow over a vertical stretching surface in the presence of a magnetic field. Hydromagnetic flow of a second-grade fluid in a channel with applications to physiological systems was investigated by Misra et al. [11]. Misra and Pal [12] have studied the hydromagnetic flow of a viscoelastic fluid in a parallel plate channel with stretching walls. The hydromagnetic fully developed laminar mixed convection flow in a vertical channel with symmetric and asymmetric wall heating conditions in the presence or absence of heat generation or absorption effects was studied by Chamkha [6].

Over the past few decades, effect of heat transfer on the flow of non-Newtonian fluids has increased significantly due to the occurrence of these fluids in industrial processes. The equations of motion of non-Newtonian fluids are highly non-linear and one order higher than the Navier-Stokes equations. The extension of the theory of Newtonian fluid mechanics to non-Newtonian fluids has proven not to be so straightforward. That is, the shear dependent viscosity and/or the elasticity of such fluids can make the theory quite complicated. Due to the complexity of the governing equations, for non-Newtonian fluids, finding accurate solutions is not easy. In this respect, the effects of fluid shear-thinning behavior on its skin friction coefficient have been well established over the years (Schowalter, 1960; Pakdemirli, 1993; Rajagopal et al., 1995). Ariel [1] has studied the laminar forced convection of a second V grade fluid through two parallel porous walls. Bhargava et al.[3] have studied the effect of magnetic field on the free convection flow of micropolar fluid between two parallel porous vertical plates. Hayat et al.[9] have studied the Hall effects on the unsteady hydromagnetic oscillatory flow of a second grade fluid. Hayat et al. [10] have investigated the influence of heat transfer on MHD second grade fluid film over an unsteady stretching sheet. Sajid et al. [16] have studied analytical

solution for the problem of fully developed mixed convection flow of viscoelastic fluid between two permeable parallel vertical walls.

In view of these, the effect of a magnetic field on the fully developed mixed convection flow of a second grade fluid in a vertical channel with permeable walls under the influence of radiation is investigated. The governing non V linear equations are solved for the velocity field and temperature field using the traditional perturbation technique. The effects of various emerging parameters on the velocity field and temperature field are discussed in detail through graphs.

2. Mathematical Formulation

We consider the laminar mixed convection flow of a second grade fluid in a vertical permeable channel, the space between the plates being h , as illustrated in Fig. 1. It is assumed that the rate of injection at one wall is equal to the rate of suction at the other wall. A uniform magnetic field B_0 is applied in the transverse direction to the flow. A rectangular coordinate system (x, y) is chosen such that the x -axis is parallel to the gravitational acceleration vector g , but with opposite direction and the y -axis is transverse to the channel walls. The left wall (i.e, at $y = 0$) is maintained at constant temperature T_1 and the right wall (i.e, at $y = h$) is maintained at constant temperature T_2 , where $T_1 > T_2$. The flow assumed steady and fully developed, i.e. the transverse velocity is zero. Then, the continuity equation drops to $\partial u / \partial x = 0$.

Fig. 1 The physical model

Viscoelastic fluids can be modeled by Rivlin-Ericksen constitutive equation

$$S = -pI + \mu A_1 + \alpha_1 A_2 + \alpha_2 A_1^2 \quad (2.1)$$

where S is the Cauchy stress tensor, p is the scalar pressure, μ, α_1 and α_2 are the material constants, customarily known as the coefficients of viscosity, elasticity and cross-viscosity, respectively. These material constants can be determined from viscometric flows for any real fluid. A_1 and A_2 are Rivlin-Ericksen tensors and they denote, respectively, the rate of strain and acceleration. A_1 and A_2 are defined by

$$A_1 = \nabla V + (\nabla V)^T \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$A_2 = \frac{dA_1}{dt} + A_1(\nabla V) + (\nabla V)^T A_1 \quad (2.3)$$

where d/dt is the material time derivative and ∇ gradient operator and $(\)^T$ transpose operator. The viscoelastic fluids when modeled by Rivlin-Ericksen constitutive equation are termed as second-grade fluids. A detailed account of the characteristics of second-grade fluids is well documented by Dunn and Rajagopal (1995). Rajagopal and Gupta (1984) have studied the thermodynamics in the form of dissipative inequality (Clausius VDuhem) and commonly accepted the idea that the specific Helmholtz free energy should be a minimum in equilibrium. From the thermodynamics consideration they assumed

$$\mu \geq 0, \quad \alpha_1 > 0, \quad \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

The basic equations of momentum and energy governing such a flow, subject to the Boussinesq approximation, are

$$\rho v_0 \frac{du}{dy} = -\frac{dp}{dx} + \mu \frac{d^2 u}{dy^2} + \alpha_1 v_0 \frac{d^3 u}{dy^3} - \sigma B_0^2 u + \rho g \beta (T - T_0) \quad (2.5)$$

$$v_0 \frac{dT}{dy} = \frac{k_1}{c_p} \frac{d^2 T}{dy^2} - \frac{1}{c_p} \frac{\partial q}{\partial y} \quad (2.6)$$

where p is the pressure, ρ is the density, μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, g is the acceleration due to gravity, β coefficient of thermal expansion, α_1 is the viscoelastic parameter, σ is the electrical conductivity, v_0 is the transpiration cross flow, velocity c_p is the specific heat at constant pressure, k_1 is the thermal conductivity and q is the

radiative heat flux. Following Cogley et al. [7], it is assumed that the fluid is optically thin with a relatively low density and the radiative heat flux is given by

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial y} = 4\alpha^2(T_0 - T) \quad (2.5)$$

here α is the mean radiation absorption coefficient.

Further, here dp/dx is a constant.

The boundary conditions are given by

$$u(0) = u(h) = 0, \quad T(0) = T_1, \quad T(h) = T_2. \quad (2.7)$$

Introducing the following non-dimensional variables

$$\bar{y} = \frac{y}{h}, \quad \bar{u} = \frac{u}{U}, \quad \theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_2 - T_0}$$

into the equations (2.5) and (2.6), we obtain

$$kR \frac{d^3 u}{dy^3} + \frac{d^2 u}{dy^2} - R \frac{du}{dy} - M^2 u + \frac{Gr}{Re} \theta + A = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

$$\frac{d^2 \theta}{dy^2} - RPr \frac{d\theta}{dy} + N^2 \theta = 0 \quad (2.9)$$

where $k = \frac{\alpha_1}{\rho h^2}$ is the viscoelastic parameter, $M = hB_0 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\mu}}$ is the Hartmann number, $R = \frac{\rho v_0 h}{\mu}$ is the cross flow Reynolds number, $Gr = \frac{g\beta(T_2 - T_1)h^3}{\nu^2}$ is the Grashof number, $Re = \frac{\rho U h}{\mu}$ is the Reynolds number, $Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}$ is the Prandtl number, $r_T = \frac{T_1 - T_0}{T_2 - T_0}$ is the wall temperature parameter, $N^2 = \frac{4\alpha^2 h^2}{k_1}$ is the radiation parameter and $A = -\left(\frac{dp}{dx}\right) \frac{U\nu}{h^2}$ is the constant pressure gradient.

The corresponding dimensionless boundary conditions are given by

$$u(0) = u(1) = 0, \quad \theta(0) = r_T, \quad \theta(1) = 1. \quad (2.10)$$

3. Perturbation Solution

We consider the first-order perturbation solution of the BVP (2.8)-(2.10) for small k . Since the constitute equation (2.1) has been derived up to only the first-order of smallness of k , therefore, the perturbation solution obtained by retaining the terms up to the same order of smallness of k must be quite logical and reasonable. We write

$$u = u_0 + k u_1 \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$\theta = \theta_0 + k\theta_1. \quad (3.2)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3.1) and (3.2) into the Eqs. (2.8) and (2.9) and boundary conditions (2.10) and then equating the like powers of k , we obtain

3.1 Zeroth-order System (k^0)

$$\frac{d^2u_0}{dy^2} - R\frac{du_0}{dy} - M^2u_0 = -\frac{Gr}{Re}\theta_0 - A \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{d^2\theta_0}{dy^2} - RPr\frac{d\theta_0}{dy} + N^2\theta_0 = 0. \quad (3.4)$$

Together with boundary conditions

$$u_0(0) = u_0(1) = 0, \quad \theta_0(0) = r_T, \quad \theta_0(1) = 1. \quad (3.5)$$

3.2 First-order System (k^1)

$$\frac{d^2u_1}{dy^2} - R\frac{du_1}{dy} - M^2u_1 = -R\frac{d^3u_0}{dy^3} - \frac{Gr}{Re}\theta_1 \quad (3.6)$$

$$\frac{d^2\theta_1}{dy^2} - RPr\frac{d\theta_1}{dy} + N^2\theta_1 = 0. \quad (3.7)$$

Together with boundary conditions

$$u_1(0) = u_1(1) = 0, \quad \theta_1(0) = 0, \quad \theta_1(1) = 0. \quad (3.8)$$

3.3 Zeroth-order Solution

Solving equations (3.3) and (3.4) using the boundary conditions (3.5), we get

$$\theta_0 = c_1e^{m_1y} + c_2e^{m_2y} \quad (3.9)$$

$$u_0 = c_3e^{m_3y} + c_4e^{m_4y} - \frac{Gr}{re}A_1e^{m_1y} - \frac{Gr}{Re}A_2e^{m_2y} + \frac{A}{M^2} \quad (3.10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= \frac{-1 + r_T e^{m_2}}{e^{m_2} - e^{m_1}}, \quad c_2 = \frac{1 - r_T}{e^{m_2} - e^{m_1}}, \quad c_3 = \frac{A_4 - A_3 e^{m_4}}{e^{m_4} - e^{m_3}}, \quad c_4 = \frac{A_3 e^{m_3} - A_4}{e^{m_4} - e^{m_3}}, \\ A_1 &= \frac{c_2}{m_1^2 - Rm_1 - M^2}, \quad A_2 = \frac{c_2}{m_2^2 - Rm_2 - M^2}, \quad A_3 = -\frac{Gr}{Re}A_1 - \frac{Gr}{Re}A_2 + \frac{A}{M^2}, \\ A_4 &= -\frac{Gr}{Re}A_1 e^{m_1} - \frac{Gr}{Re}A_2 e^{m_2} + \frac{A}{M^2}, \quad m_1 = (RPr + \sqrt{R^2Pr^2 - 4N^2})/2, \\ m_2 &= (RPr - \sqrt{R^2Pr^2 - 4N^2})/2, \quad m_3 = (R + \sqrt{R^2 + 4M^2})/2 \quad \text{and} \\ m_4 &= (R - \sqrt{R^2 + 4M^2})/2. \end{aligned}$$

3.4 First-order Solution

Solving Eq. (3.7) with corresponding boundary conditions, we obtain

$$\theta_1 = 0. \tag{3.11}$$

Substituting the equations (3.10) and (3.11) into the Eq. (3.6) and then solving the resulting equation with the corresponding conditions, we get

$$u_1 = c_5 e^{m_3 y} + c_6 e^{m_4 y} - A_{11} y e^{m_3 y} - A_{12} y e^{m_4 y} + A_{13} e^{m_1 y} + A_{14} e^{m_2 y} \tag{3.12}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} c_5 &= \frac{A_{10} - A_9 e^{m_4}}{e^{m_4} - e^{m_3}}, \quad c_6 = \frac{A_9 e^{m_3} - A_{10}}{e^{m_4} - e^{m_3}}, \quad A_5 = c_3 m_3^3, \quad A_6 = c_4 m_4^3, \\ A_7 &= \frac{Gr}{Re} A_1 m_1^3, \quad A_8 = \frac{Gr}{re} A_2 m_2^3, \quad A_9 = \frac{RA_7}{m_1^2 - Rm_1 - M^2} + \frac{RA_8}{m_2^2 - Rm_2 - M^2}, \\ A_{10} &= -\frac{RA_5 e^{m_3}}{2m_3 - R} - \frac{RA_6 e^{m_4}}{2m_4 - R} + \frac{RA_7 e^{m_1}}{m_1^2 - Rm_1 - M^2} + \frac{RA_8 e^{m_2}}{m_2^2 - Rm_2 - M^2}, \quad A_{11} = \frac{RA_5}{2m_3 - R}, \\ A_{12} &= \frac{RA_6}{2m_4 - R}, \quad A_{13} = \frac{RA_7}{m_1^2 - Rm_1 - M^2} \quad \text{and} \quad A_{14} = \frac{RA_8}{m_2^2 - Rm_2 - M^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the perturbation solutions up to first order for θ and u are given by

$$\theta = \theta_0 + k\theta_1 = c_1 e^{m_1 y} + c_2 e^{m_2 y} \tag{3.13}$$

and

$$u = u_0 + k u_1. \tag{3.14}$$

The skin friction τ at the plate $y = 0$ of the channel is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = c_3 m_3 + c_4 m_4 - \frac{Gr}{Re} A_1 m_1 - \frac{Gr}{Re} A_2 m_2 \\ &+ k(c_5 m_3 + c_6 m_4 - A_{11} - A_{12} + A_{13} m_1 + A_{14} m_2) \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

The rate of heat transfer coefficient in terms of Nusselt number Nu at the plate $y = 0$ of the channel is given by

$$Nu = \left. \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = c_1 m_1 + c_2 m_2. \tag{3.16}$$

Note that when $k = 0, R = 0, N \rightarrow 0$ and $M \rightarrow 0$ our results reduces to those given by Aung and Worku (1986).

4. Discussion of the Results

In order to see the effects of M, k, N, R, Pr, Gr, Re and r_T on the velocity u , we have plotted Figs. 2-10.

Fig (2) depicts the variation of the velocity u with respect to y for various values of visco-elastic parameter $k = 0, 0.01, 0.02$. This figure corresponds to $r_T = 0.5, M = 1, R = 5, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. From the figure it is found that the velocity u decreases with an increase in k . The point where the maximum velocity occurs is shifted away from the upper wall as the values of the visco-elastic parameter (k) are increased. Also it is observed that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. Fig (3) illustrates the effect of Radiation parameter N on the velocity u . the graph is drawn for the values $r_T = 0.5, M = 1, R = 5, A = 1, k = 0.01, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. From the figure it is noticed that the velocity u increases with an increase in Radiation parameter N . Also it is found that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y increases. Fig (4) shows the variation of the velocity u with respect to y for the various values of Hartmann number M . This figure corresponds to $k = 0.01, R = 5, r_T = 0.5, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. From the figure it is observed that the velocity u decreases with increasing Hartmann number M . Also it is noted that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. Fig (5) communicates the effect of cross-flow Reynolds number R on the velocity u for the values $r_T = 0.5, M = 1, k = 0.01, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. From the figure it is seen that the velocity u decreases with increasing cross-flow Reynolds number R . Also it is observed that as y increases the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases. Fig (6) shows the variation of the velocity u with respect to y for the various values of Prandtl number $Pr = 0.2, 0.71, 7$. This figure corresponds to $M = 0.1, r_T = 0.5, R = 5, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, k = 0.02$ and $Re = 1$. From the figure it is found that the velocity u decreases on increasing Prandtl number Pr . Also it is seen that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. Fig (7) shows the variation of the velocity u with respect to y for the various values of Grashof number $Gr = 2, 1, 0$. This figure corresponds to $r_T = 0.5, R = 5, M = 1, N = 1, k = 0.01, A = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. From the figure it is observed that the velocity u increases with increasing Grashof number Gr . Also it is noted that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances from left wall to right wall. Fig (8) depicts

the effect of Reynolds number Re on the velocity u with respect to y . This figure is drawn for $M = 1, r_T = 0.5, R = 5, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71, A = 1, k = 0.01$ and $Re = 1$. It is noted that the velocity u decreases with increasing Reynolds number Re . Also it is observed that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. Fig (9) communicates the effect of wall temperature parameter r_T on the velocity u with respect to y . This figure corresponds to $M = 1, k = 0.02, N = 1, R = 5, A = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. It is observed that the velocity u increases with increasing r_T . Also it is seen that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y increases. Fig (10) demonstrates the variation of the velocity u with respect to y for the various values of Pressure constant $A = 3, 2, 1$. This figure corresponds to $M = 1, k = 0.02, N = 1, R = 5, r_T = 0.5, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$. It is seen that the velocity u increases with an increase in Pressure constant A . From the figure it is also seen that the velocity u firstly increases and then decreases as y advances from left wall to right wall.

In order to see the effects of N, R, Pr and r_T on the temperature θ , we have plotted Figs. 11-14. Fig (11) shows the variation of the temperature with respect to y for the various values of radiation parameter $N = 2, 1, 0$. This figure corresponds to $R = 5, r_T = 0.5$ and $Pr = 0.71$. From the figure it is observed that the temperature increases with increasing radiation parameter N . For $N = 0, 1$ the temperature always increases as y advances while for $N = 2$, it firstly increases and then decreases as y advances. Fig (12) depicts the effect of cross-flow Reynolds number R on the temperature. This figure corresponds for $N = 1, r_T = 0.5$ and $Pr = 0.71$. It is found that the temperature decreases with increasing cross-flow Reynolds number R . Fig (13) communicates the effect of Prandtl number Pr on the temperature with respect to y . This figure corresponds for the values $N = 1, r_T = 0.5$ and $R = 5$. From the figure it is observed that the temperature increases with increasing Prandtl number Pr . Fig (14) shows the variation of the temperature with respect to y for various values of $r_T = 0.8, 0.5, 0$. This figure corresponds for $N = 1, R = 5$ and $Pr = 0.71$. It is noticed that the temperature increases with increasing wall temperature parameter (r_T). Also in this figure it is observed that the graphs begin from the different values of when $y=0$ and they coincide when $y = 1$.

Fig. 2. Effect of viscoelastic parameter k on u for $r_f = 0.5, M = 1, R = 5, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$.

Fig. 3. Effect of Radiation parameter N on u for $r_f = 0.5, M = 1, R = 5, A = 1, k = 0.01, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$.

Fig. 4. Effect of Hartmann number M on u for $k = 0.01, R = 5, r_f = 0.5, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$.

Fig. 5. Effect of R on u for $r_f = 0.5, M = 1, k = 0.01, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$.

Fig. 6. Effect of Prandtl number Pr on u for $M = 0.1, r_f = 0.5, R = 5, A = 1, N = 1, Gr = 1, k = 0.02$ and $Re = 1$.

Fig. 7. Effect of Grashof number Gr on u for $r_f = 0.5, R = 5, M = 1, N = 1, k = 0.01, A = 1, Pr = 0.71$ and $Re = 1$.

Fig. 8. Effect of Reynolds number Re on u for $M=1, \tau_f=0.5, R=5, N=1, Gr=1, Pr=0.71, A=1, k=0.01$ and $Re=1$.

Fig. 9. Effect of wall temperature parameter τ_f on u for $M=1, k=0.02, N=1, R=5, A=1, Gr=1, Pr=0.71$ and $Re=1$.

Fig. 10. Effect of pressure constant A on u for $M=1, k=0.02, N=1, R=5, \tau_f=0.5, Gr=1, Pr=0.71$ and $Re=1$.

Fig. 11. Effect of N on θ for $R=5, \tau_f=0.5$ and $Pr=0.71$.

Fig. 12. Effect of R on θ for $N=1, \tau_f=0.5$ and $Pr=0.71$.

Fig. 13. Effect of Pr on θ for $N=1, \tau_f=0.5$ and $R=5$.

Fig. 14. Effect of r_T on θ for $N=1, R=5$ and $Pr=0.71$.

Table-1 : The skin friction τ at the plate $y = 0$ of the channel

k	N	M	R	Pr	Gr	Re	r_T	A	τ
0.01	1	1	5	0.71	1	1	0.5	1	0.2800
0.02	1	1	5	0.71	1	1	0.5	1	0.2709
0.01	2	1	5	0.71	1	1	0.5	1	0.2956
0.01	1	2	5	0.71	1	1	0.5	1	0.2614
0.01	1	1	8	0.71	1	1	0.5	1	0.1842
0.01	1	1	5	7	1	1	0.5	1	0.2731
0.01	1	1	5	0.71	2	1	0.5	1	0.3782
0.01	1	1	5	0.71	1	2	0.5	1	0.2309
0.01	1	1	5	0.71	1	1	0.8	1	0.3341
0.01	1	1	5	0.71	1	1	0.5	2	0.4617

Table-2 : The rate of heat transfer coefficient in terms of Nusselt number Nu at the plate $y = 0$ of the channel

N	R	Pr	r_T	Nu
1	5	0.71	0.5	0.1929
2	5	0.71	0.5	0.7339
1	8	0.71	0.5	0.0997
1	5	7	0.5	0.0143
1	5	0.71	0.8	0.2360

Table-1 shows the effects of $N, M, k, R, Pr, Gr, Re, A$ and r_T on the skin friction τ . From Table-1, it is found that the skin friction τ decreases with increasing k, N, M, R, Pr and Re , whereas it increases with increasing Gr, r_T and A . Table-2 depicts the effects of N, R, Pr and r_T on Nusselt number Nu . From Table-2, it is observed that the Nusselt number Nu decreases with increasing N, R and r_T , while it increases with increasing Pr .

5. Conclusions

In this chapter, the effect of radiation and magnetic field on the fully developed mixed convection flow of a second grade fluid in a vertical channel with permeable walls is investigated. The governing non-linear equations are solved for the velocity field and temperature field using the traditional perturbation technique. It is found that, the velocity u decreases with increasing k, M, R, Re and Pr , while it increases with increasing N, Gr and r_T . Also, it is observed that, the temperature θ decreases with increasing R and Pr , while it increases with increasing N and r_T .

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